

Optical Sensors Utilizing Resonant Modes in Total Reflection Structures.

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Use of the resonant modes that exist within a Gires-Tournois interferometer as a basis for optical sensing applications is examined. A novel technique, which has simplicity as a primary attribute, can sense relatively small changes in refractive index in a thin film on the order of 1×10^{-4} . Typically sensing techniques in the reflection geometry rely on the use of surface plasmon resonances to provide the means to detect changes in the surrounding environment. Here we utilize the leaky wave type resonances present in structures composed of purely dielectric layers at the total internal reflection (TIR) surface of a prism. Leaky wave resonances in these structures are typically more sensitive to changes in the refractive index than the plasmon resonances as has been noted (4). This structure and experiment are meant to test the refractive index sensitivity of the resonant structure which is due to the redistribution of the incident fields (laser beam) when the incident light is coincident with a resonance condition of the leaky wave structure. The amount of this Goos-Hanchen shifting is determined by the characteristics of the cavity but this use of the lateral shift is more sensitive than utilizing the entire resonance width to provide the dynamic optical range.

The sample is constructed by spin coating a 2.1 micron thick layer of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) onto the face of a higher index prism (SFL11, $n=1.78$). A He-Ne laser beam clipped with a knife edge is incident on the cavity at the resonance angle nearest TIR cutoff between the prism and the PMMA film (see figure 1). This resonance provides the maximum sensitivity to index changes in the film. The knife edge diffraction pattern is imaged by a 20X microscope objective after the beam exits the sample. The imaged pattern shifts with the Goos-Hanchen shifting of the beam inside the sample and the amount of index change required for a full lateral shift of one of the fringes by one fringe width is the desired measure of the film's suitability as a sensor. This corresponds to a switching of the light intensity from maximum to a minimum at given fixed spatial point within the diffraction pattern. Refractive index of the PMMA film is modulated via temperature changes as the sample is placed within a temperature controlled enclosure. The thermo-optic coefficient of PMMA is well known and index changes in the film are inferred from the changes in temperature. The enclosure and sample are allowed to achieve thermal equilibrium over many hours as the temperature is varied by only a few degrees celsius. It is found that a 2 degree C change in temperature is adequate to produce an observable fringe shift of one full fringe width. This corresponds to 3×10^{-4} change in refractive index approximately. This was the amount required for a one full fringe width, however this is not the lower limit of sensitivity as fractional shifts in the fringes are easily observed.

This type of optical cavity is very easy to construct and the arrangement is a suitable means to use as a detection scheme for almost any type of sensing film that can be deposited into the experimental arrangement.

Figure 1. The angular position of three of the resonances within the cavity. The reflectance dips due to the presence of a small amount of material and scattering loss within the polymer layer (modeled index= $1.47+0.0005i$). The resonance at approximately 55 degrees incidence was the one used in the study.

Figure 2. Experimental arrangement. The sample is placed in a temperature controlled enclosure.

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